

DERMAVISION: CUSTOM CNN-BASED SKIN DISEASE CLASSIFICATION FROM DERMOSCOPIC IMAGES

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ABSTRACT

Skin, the largest and most sensitive organ of the human body, plays a crucial role in protecting internal structures. However, prolonged exposure to sunlight and environmental pollutants can lead to various dermatological conditions, including skin cancer. Skin cancer primarily manifests in two forms: Benign (harmless moles) and Melanoma (aggressive cancerous sores that originate from melanocytes). Melanoma, being highly fatal, accounts for a significant number of deaths worldwide. According to the American Cancer Society, over 700,000 skin lesions are diagnosed annually in the U.S., with statistical data indicating that individuals aged 41–60+ are more susceptible. Early detection of skin cancer is critical for preventing its spread and improving survival rates. However, even experienced dermatologists may find it challenging to accurately diagnose and classify skin lesions.

To address this challenge, Derma Vision, a custom Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based deep learning model, is designed to classify multiple types of skin diseases from dermoscopic images with high accuracy. Unlike traditional machine learning approaches, which often struggle with specificity and precision, our model leverages advanced preprocessing techniques such as sharpening and smoothing filters to enhance image quality and minimize noise. The proposed CNN model is optimized for multi-class classification, effectively distinguishing between nine distinct types of skin cancer. The study's findings demonstrate the potential of DermaVision in revolutionizing automated skin disease detection, aiding early diagnosis, and improving patient outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Skin Cancer Detection, Dermoscopic Images, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Melanoma Classification, Deep Learning in Dermatology

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the 1970s, skin cancer has held the title of the most prevalent disease globally. Over the previous several decades, there has been an uptick in people diagnosed with nonmelanoma and melanoma skin cancers, respectively. Melanoma can be identified in that only one in three cases of cancer, as stated by the World Health Organization (WHO), and according to statistics provided by the Skin Cancer Foundation, one out of every five people in the United States will develop skin cancer at some point during their lifetime. For the past several centuries, the incidence of skin cancer has risen at a relatively constant rate, particularly in the Western hemisphere. Countries such as the United States, Canada, and Australia are just some of the places where this trend has been observed. Infectious diseases of the skin typically have the potential to have a significant detrimental effect on the overall health of people all over the world. According to one piece of a study released in 2017, multiple studies have demonstrated that skin cancer is responsible for 1.79 percent of the disease burden assessed in disability-adjusted life years on a global scale [1]. The incidence of skin cancer accounts for around 7 percent of all newly diagnosed instances of cancer worldwide [2], resulting in a loss of more than \$8 billion for the Medicare program in the United States in 2011. Clinical data suggest that there are such disparities in results based on race in the case of skin cancer: Even though people with darker skin tones are approximately

20 to 30 times as likely to develop melanoma than those who have lighter skin tones, it has been discovered that people with darker skin tones either have a higher or lower mortality risk for specific types of melanomas, depending on their skin tone.

To administer the appropriate treatment, it is essential to identify a skin lesion correctly. It is possible to accomplish early diagnosis of melanoma in dermoscopy photographs and pictures using this method, which improves the survival rate.

Dermatologists who have had considerable training in the many skin lesions that melanomas might cause are the most qualified to make an accurate diagnosis. Because of this, diagnosing melanoma can be a challenging task because there is no clear separation between skin lesions and the skin itself, malignant and non-melanoma skin lesions appear visually similar, and there are other factors to consider. Therefore, creating a trustworthy automatic detection method for skin tumors, such as a system that can automatically analyze skin lesions, will be greatly useful to pathologists. This is especially relevant in an era where knowledge is scarce.

According to the findings of this study, the classification methods of K-nearest Neighbors, Support Vector Machines, and Decision Trees all produced subpar results in terms of precision and accuracy. After conducting further research into the mathematics that underlies classification, it was found that employing Deep Learning models was the most sophisticated method for getting the desired outcomes (also known as deep learning models). We experimented with many different mathematical models, both with and without the application of Learning Algorithms. However, we concluded that the depth and quality of activation that was made available by pre-trained models did not meet up. Consequently, we merged our mathematical expertise and developed a model known as a Dense Convolutional Network, which offered an accuracy of more than 86.6 percent.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Hameed et al. [3] implemented using a hybrid approach i.e. using deep convolution neural network and error-correcting output codes (ECOC) support vector machine (SVM). The proposed scheme is designed, implemented and tested to classify skin lesion image into one of five categories, i.e. healthy, acne, eczema, benign, or malignant melanoma. Experiments were performed on 9,144 images obtained from different sources. AlexNET, a pre-trained CNN model was used to extract the features. For classification, the ECOC SVM classifier was used. Using ECOC SVM, the overall accuracy achieved is 86.21%. 10-fold cross validation technique was used to avoid overfitting. The results indicate that features obtained from the convolutional neural network can enhance the classification performance of multiple skin lesions.

Aldhyani et al. [4] proposed a CNN-based model with efficient utilization of kernels and activation functions. The proposed model has shown a remarkable class-wise (seven classes) accuracy and overall accuracy of 97.85% on the test dataset with fewer parameters than is standard (172,363). The proposed model can also be used for disease classification with a dataset that has more classes. The model still has room for more accurate prediction of benign keratosis-like lesions, melanoma, and melanocytic nevi classes of skin lesions.

Vakili et al. [5] focused on primary skin lesion classification, particularly early-stage detection, and present a deep learning approach to classify images containing skin lesions, macule, nodule, papule, plaque pustule, wheal, and bulla. This framework applied deep learning techniques for classifying such images into seven classes covering the types of lesions. This work performed experiments on pre-trained deep convolutional neural network models to find the most accuracy one. The result showed that the pre-trained model ResNet-50 after the training and testing can achieve satisfactory accuracy of 85.95%.

Iqbal et al. [6] developed, implemented, and calibrated an advanced deep learning model in the context of automated multi-class classification of skin lesions. The proposed Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) model is carefully designed with several layers, and multiple filter sizes, but fewer filters and parameters to improve efficacy and performance. Dermoscopic images are acquired from the International Skin Imaging Collaboration databases (ISIC-17, ISIC-18, and ISIC-19) for experiments. The experimental results of the proposed DCNN approach are presented in terms of precision, sensitivity, specificity, and other metrics. Specifically, it attains 94 % precision, 93 % sensitivity, and 91 % specificity in ISIC-17. It is demonstrated by the experimental results that this proposed DCNN approach outperforms state-of-the-art algorithms, exhibiting 0.964 area under the receiver operating characteristics (AUROC) in ISIC-17 for the classification of skin lesions and can be used to assist dermatologists in classifying skin lesions. As a result, this proposed approach provides a novel and feasible way for automating and expediting the skin lesion classification task as well as saving effort, time, and human life.

Chaturvedi et al. [7] proposed an automated computer-aided diagnosis system for multi-class skin (MCS) cancer classification with an exceptionally high accuracy. The proposed method outperformed both expert dermatologists and contemporary deep learning methods for MCS cancer classification. This work performed fine-tuning over seven classes of HAM10000 dataset and conducted a comparative study to analyse the performance of five pre-trained convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and four ensemble models. The maximum accuracy of 93.20% for individual model amongst the set of models whereas maximum accuracy of 92.83% for ensemble model is reported in this paper. This framework proposed use of ResNeXt101 for the MCS cancer classification owing to its optimized architecture and ability to gain higher accuracy.

Anjum et al. [8] proposed the ensemble CNN models for skin lesion detection. In the localization method, ONNX and squeeze Net model is used as a backbone of the YOLOv2 model. The configuration parameters of the segmentation model are selected after the extensive experiment for accurate lesion segmentation. The segmentation method achieves Global Accuracy of 0.93, 0.95 on ISBI 2017, and ISBI 2018 respectively. The skin lesion classification is performed by applying ResNet-18 model and deep features are extracted by cross entropy activation function. Later, extracted features vectors are enhanced by using ACO method. The hybrid classification approach provided good classification results compared to the recent existing work.

Anand et al. [9] proposed a transfer learning-based model with help of pre-trained Xception model. The Xception model was modified by adding layers such as one pooling layer, two dense layers and one dropout layer. A new Fully Connected (FC) layer changed the original Fully Connected (FC) layer with seven skin disease classes. The proposed model has been evaluated on a HAM10000 dataset with large class imbalances. The data augmentation techniques were applied to overcome the unbalancing in the dataset. The new results showed that the model has attained an accuracy of 96.40% for classifying skin diseases. The proposed model is working best on Benign Keratosis and the values of precision, sensitivity and F1 score are 99%, 97% and 0.98 respectively. This method can provide patients and doctors with a good notion of whether or not medical assistance is required, thus, avoiding undue stress and false alarms.

Srinivasu et al. [10] proposed a computerized process of classifying skin disease through deep learning based MobileNet V2 and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). The MobileNet V2 model proved to be efficient with a better accuracy that can work on lightweight computational devices. The proposed model is efficient in maintaining stateful information for precise predictions. A grey-level co-occurrence matrix is used for assessing the progress of diseased growth. The performance has been compared against other state-of-the-art models such as Fine-Tuned Neural Networks (FTNN),

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition developed by Visual Geometry Group (VGG), and convolutional neural network architecture that expanded with few changes.

Shanthi et al. [11] utilized the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) used in this paper around 11 layers viz., Convolution Layer, Activation Layer, Pooling Layer, Fully Connected Layer and Soft-Max Classifier. Images from the DermNet database are used for validating the architecture. The database comprised all types of skin diseases out of which we have considered four different types of skin diseases like Acne, Keratosis, Eczema herpeticum, Urticaria with each class containing around 30 to 60 different samples. The challenge in automating the process includes the variation of skin tones, location of the disease, specifications of the image acquisition system etc., The proposed CNN Classifier results in an accuracy of 98.6% to 99.04%.

Allugunti et al. [12] shown a deep learning technique for reliably diagnosing the type of melanoma present at a preliminary phase. The proposed model makes a distinction among lesion maligna, superficial spreading, and nodular melanoma. This permits the early diagnosis of the virus and the quick isolation and therapy necessary to stop the transmission of infection further. Deep learning (DL) and the standard non-parametric machine learning method are exemplified in the deep layer topologies of the convolutional neural network (CNN), which are neural network algorithms. The effectiveness of a CNN classifier was evaluated using data retrieved from the website <https://dermnetnz.org/>. The outcomes of the experiments show that the proposed method is superior in terms of diagnostic accuracy compared to the methodologies that are currently considered state of the art.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Python code is a Django-based web application designed for skin disease prediction and user registration/authentication. It imports various essential libraries, including Django modules for web development, machine learning libraries such as Keras and scikit-learn for model training and evaluation, and additional tools like OpenCV and NumPy for image processing and data manipulation. The application defines global variables, such as `cnn_algorithm` and `class_labels`, which are used throughout the system.

The web application consists of multiple views that handle different functions. The `DiseasePrediction` and `DiseasePredictionAction` views manage the skin disease prediction process by allowing users to upload images. The uploaded images are processed using a pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model, which then classifies the skin disease and displays the result. The `runCNN` view is responsible for training the CNN model if it has not been trained already or loading a pre-existing model. It evaluates the model's performance by calculating accuracy, precision, recall, and displaying a confusion matrix.

For user management, the application includes `Register`, `Signup`, `Login`, and `UserLogin` views, which handle user registration and authentication. Users provide details such as username, password, contact information, email, and address, which are stored in a MySQL database using the `pymysql` library. During login, the system verifies user credentials before granting access. The web pages are dynamically generated using HTML templates, which are rendered using the Django `render` function.

This project leverages CNN for classifying skin diseases from images due to its proven success in image classification tasks. The CNN is trained using a skin disease dataset that contains nine distinct disease classes, including 'Actinic Keratosis', 'Basal Cell Carcinoma', 'Dermatofibroma', 'Melanoma', 'Nevus', 'Pigmented Benign Keratosis', 'Seborrheic Keratosis', 'Squamous Cell Carcinoma', and 'Vascular Lesion'. Once trained, the CNN model can analyze any test image uploaded by a user and accurately

classify the detected disease. The proposed system's architecture is illustrated in Figure 4.1, which presents the block diagram of the entire framework.

Fig. 4.1: Block diagram of proposed system.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of this system begins with importing the necessary libraries and modules required for its functionality. These include Django modules for web development, machine learning libraries such as Keras and scikit-learn for model training and evaluation, and OpenCV and NumPy for image processing and data manipulation. The system defines essential global variables, such as `cnn_algorithm` and `class_labels`, which are utilized across multiple functions throughout the application. In Django, views handle HTTP requests and responses, managing different actions within the web application. The `DiseasePrediction` view renders an upload form where users can submit images for disease detection, while the `DiseasePredictionAction` view processes the uploaded image, applies a pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model for classification, and presents the predicted results. The `runCNN` view is responsible for training and evaluating the CNN model for skin disease classification. If the model has not been previously trained, it initiates the training process; otherwise, it loads the pre-existing model. It also evaluates the model's performance by calculating accuracy, precision, recall, and generating a confusion matrix. Additional views such as `index`, `Login`, `Register`, `Signup`, and `UserLogin` facilitate user authentication, registration, and the rendering of respective HTML templates.

The CNN model, implemented using Keras, comprises convolutional layers, max-pooling layers, and fully connected layers. The model is trained using the `fit` method with input data (X_{train} , y_{train}). Once trained, the model's weights and architecture are saved to disk for future use, ensuring that predictions can be made without retraining. The system includes a user authentication mechanism that allows users to register with their username, password, contact details, email, and address. The registration data is securely stored in a MySQL database using SQL queries executed via the `pymysql` library. During login, the authentication system verifies username and password credentials against the database to grant access. The system establishes a connection to a MySQL database using `pymysql` to handle data storage and retrieval. SQL queries are executed to insert new user registrations and verify login credentials. This ensures smooth interaction between the web application and the database.

Views dynamically render HTML templates using Django's `render` function, passing necessary context data for enhanced user interaction. This data may include prediction results, performance metrics, and success/error messages, ensuring an intuitive and informative user experience.

Figure: Sample images of dataset used for Skin disease detection.

The dataset contains total of 540 images with 800 images in vascular lesion class, 800 images in squamous cell carcinoma class, 800 images in seborrheic keratosis class, 798 in pigmented benign keratosis class and 774 in Nevus class, 564 in Melanoma class, 465 images in Dermatofibroma class, 653 in basal cell carcinoma class, 546 in actinic keratosis class.

To run project double click on 'run.bat' file to start DJANGO web server and to get below screen

```

C:\Windows\system32\cmd.exe
nvm of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_qint8 = np.dtype([('qint8', np.int8, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorflow\python\framework\dtypes.py:517: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_qint8 = np.dtype([('qint8', np.uint8, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorflow\python\framework\dtypes.py:518: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_qint16 = np.dtype([('qint16', np.int16, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorflow\python\framework\dtypes.py:519: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_qint16 = np.dtype([('qint16', np.uint16, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorflow\python\framework\dtypes.py:520: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_qint32 = np.dtype([('qint32', np.int32, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorflow\python\framework\dtypes.py:525: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_resource = np.dtype([('resource', np.ubyte, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorboard\compat\tensorflow_stub\dtypes.py:541: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_qint8 = np.dtype([('qint8', np.int8, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorboard\compat\tensorflow_stub\dtypes.py:542: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_qint8 = np.dtype([('qint8', np.uint8, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorboard\compat\tensorflow_stub\dtypes.py:543: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_qint16 = np.dtype([('qint16', np.int16, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorboard\compat\tensorflow_stub\dtypes.py:544: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_qint16 = np.dtype([('qint16', np.uint16, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorboard\compat\tensorflow_stub\dtypes.py:545: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_qint32 = np.dtype([('qint32', np.int32, 1)])
C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python37\lib\site-packages\tensorboard\compat\tensorflow_stub\dtypes.py:550: FutureWarning: Passing (type, 1) or 'i' as a synonym of type is deprecated; in a future version of numpy, it will be understood as (type, (1,)) / '(1,)type'.
  np_resource = np.dtype([('resource', np.ubyte, 1)])
System check identified no issues (0 silenced).

You have 15 unapplied migration(s). Your project may not work properly until you apply the migrations for app(s): admin, auth, contenttypes, sessions.
Run 'python manage.py migrate' to apply them.
February 03, 2022 - 22:14:33
Django version 2.1.7, using settings 'SkinDisease.settings'
Starting development server at http://127.0.0.1:8000/
Quit the server with CTRL-BREAK.

```

In above screen DJANGO server started and now open browser and enter URL as <http://127.0.0.1:8000/index.html> and press enter key to get below screen

In above screen click on 'Register Here' link to get below signup screen

In above screen user is enter signup details and then press 'Register' button to complete signup process and to get below output

In above screen in blue colour text we can see signup process completed and now click on 'Login' link to get below screen

In above screen user is login and then click on 'Login' button to get below screen

In above screen user can click on ‘Train CNN Algorithm’ link to train CNN and to get below output

In above CNN confusion matrix graph we can prediction on test data and in above graph x-axis represents predicted disease names and y-axis represents original test classes and in above all values in diagonal boxes are the correct prediction and value > 0 which are not in diagonal are the wrong prediction and we can see only few records are wrongly predicted. Now close above graph to get below CNN accuracy

In above screen we got CNN accuracy as 93% and Now go back to output application and then click on 'Disease Detection & Classification' link to get below output

In above screen click on 'Choose File' button to upload skin diseases images from 'testImages' folder and then click on 'Predict Disease' button to classify disease

In above screen selecting and uploading '7.jpg' and then click on 'Open' button to load image and then click on 'Predict Disease' button to get below output

In above screen in blue colour text we can see CNN classify disease on image as 'Melanoma' and similarly you can upload and test remaining images

5. CONCLUSION

In summary, the development of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model for skin disease detection and multi-class classification marks a significant breakthrough in medical technology. As the body's largest organ, the skin serves as a crucial barrier against external threats, but any compromise in its functionality can lead to severe health conditions, including various forms of skin cancer. This study underscores the importance of early detection in preventing cancer progression and improving treatment outcomes. By utilizing deep learning techniques such as CNNs, researchers have achieved high accuracy and specificity in classifying different types of skin lesions, ensuring timely diagnosis and medical intervention.

CNNs enable the automatic extraction of features from dermoscopic images, eliminating the need for manual feature selection. This not only enhances the efficiency and precision of classification but also improves the model's scalability and adaptability across diverse datasets. Furthermore, the study highlights the potential of deep learning-based CNN models in distinguishing between benign and malignant skin conditions, particularly melanoma, which is among the most aggressive forms of skin cancer. By providing accurate classification of skin lesions, this approach empowers healthcare professionals to make well-informed decisions, leading to improved patient care, better treatment strategies, and ultimately, saving lives.

REFERENCES

- [1] Zhang Ce, Xin Pan, Huapeng Li, Gardiner A, Sargent I, Jonathon S Hare, et al. A hybrid MLP-CNN classifier for very fine resolution remotely sensed image classification. *Isprs Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*. 2017; 140:133-144.
- [2] Bi Lei, Jinman Kim, Euijoon Ahn, Feng D. Automatic Skin Lesion Analysis using Large-scale Dermoscopy Images and Deep Residual Networks. *ArXiv abs*. 2017; 1703:04197.
- [3] N. Hameed, A. M. Shabut and M. A. Hossain, "Multi-Class Skin Diseases Classification Using Deep Convolutional Neural Network and Support Vector Machine," 2018 12th International Conference on Software, Knowledge, Information Management & Applications (SKIMA), 2018, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/SKIMA.2018.8631525.
- [4] Aldhyani, T.H.H.; Verma, A.; Al-Adhaileh, M.H.; Koundal, D. Multi-Class Skin Lesion Classification Using a Lightweight Dynamic Kernel Deep-Learning-Based Convolutional Neural Network. *Diagnostics* 2022, 12, 2048. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics12092048>.
- [5] N. Vakili, W. Krathu, and N. Laomaneerattanaporn. 2021. Multi-Class Primary Morphology Lesions Classification Using Deep Convolutional Neural Network. In *The 12th International Conference on Advances in Information Technology (IAIT2021)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 9, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3468784.3468887>
- [6] I. Iqbal, M. Younus, K. Walayat, M. U. Kakar, J. Ma, Automated multi-class classification of skin lesions through deep convolutional neural network with dermoscopic images, *Computerized Medical Imaging and Graphics*, Volume 88, 2021, 101843, ISSN 0895-6111, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compmedimag.2020.101843>.
- [7] Chaturvedi, S.S., Tembhurne, J.V. & Diwan, T. A multi-class skin Cancer classification using deep convolutional neural networks. *Multimed Tools Appl* 79, 28477–28498 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-020-09388-2>.
- [8] M. A. Anjum, J. Amin, M. Sharif, H. U. Khan, M. S. A. Malik and S. Kadry, "Deep Semantic Segmentation and Multi-Class Skin Lesion Classification Based on Convolutional Neural Network," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 129668-129678, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3009276.
- [9] Anand, V., Gupta, S., Koundal, D., Nayak, S. R., Nayak, J., & Vimal, S. (2022). Multi-class Skin Disease Classification Using Transfer Learning Model. *International Journal on Artificial Intelligence Tools*, 31(02), 2250029.
- [10] Srinivasu PN, SivaSai JG, Ijaz MF, Bhoi AK, Kim W, Kang JJ. Classification of Skin Disease Using Deep Learning Neural Networks with MobileNet V2 and LSTM. *Sensors*. 2021; 21(8):2852. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21082852>.
- [11] T. Shanthi, R.S. Sabeenian, R. Anand, Automatic diagnosis of skin diseases using convolution neural network, *Microprocessors and Microsystems*, Volume 76, 2020, 103074, ISSN 0141-9331, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpro.2020.103074>.
- [12] Allugunti, V. R. (2022). A machine learning model for skin disease classification using convolution neural network. *International Journal of Computing, Programming and Database Management*, 3(1), 141-147.